

HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONAL'S ATTITUDES TOWARDS SAFE AND HYGIENIC PRACTICE IN THE HOSPITAL

AUXILIYA PREETHI^{M1}, SAKTHIABINAYA. S² and MANO SAMUELRAJ³

^{1,2}MBA Student, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Science (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai.

³Assistant Professor, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai. Email id: manosamuelraj.ssm@saveetha.com

ABSTRACT:

The research paper titled a study on health care professional's attitudes towards safe and hygienic practice in the hospital. Descriptive research is applied using simple random sampling technique with 60 respondents. The aim of this article is to study the health care professional's attitudes towards safe and hygienic practice in the hospital with the best innovative treatments and health wellbeing of an individual. Safe and hygienic practice is very vital in health care setting to eradicate or eliminate the medical errors, incidents and harmful treatments and procedures.

Key words: Health care professionals, Safe and hygienic practice, Attitude, Innovation and wellbeing, Medical errors, Incidents, harmful treatments.

INTRODUCTION

Patient protection and prevention of medical errors is being seen as a progressively vital issue in the medical industry. The growing number of hazardous and insanitary measures may carry a challenge for healthcare administration. So, it is significant to learn better about primary care provider's attitudes towards patient's protection. Prevention of adverse effects, harm to patients and medical errors is a major constituent of providing high health care quality services. In a modern medicine, it is well recognized that patient protection is a key constituent of innovative care services and will leads to human wellbeing of an individual. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

Safe and hygienic practices in clinical setup is play a vital role to reduce the adverse effects of treatments and procedures, incidents and medical errors. Non- performance to preserve patient safety provokes the significant raise in the cost of treatments, morbidity and mortality rates. To study the health care professional's attitudes towards safe and hygienic practice in the hospital.

Objectives:

- To study the attitude of employees towards safe and hygienic practice.
- To assess the level of influence of demographic variables on employee attitude towards patient safety.

- To study the significant relationship between the attitudes of employees towards safe and hygienic practice with respect to Gender, work position, regular shift and place of work.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

(Indre Brasaitė et.al, 2016) This paper talks about a study of health care professional's attitudes towards patient safety Cross-sectional, quantitative research study, self-administered questionnaire in health care professionals. The results showed that high positive attitude towards patient safety with related factors.

(Rachel E Davis et.al, 2012) This article talks about patient's and frontline workers attitudes towards the restricted extremity or limb alert patient safety video. A dependent groups design, preliminary and post-questionnaire of patient safety video was used in this study with video-assisted teaching to the patients. Data was collected to doctors and nurses. The results showed that patients and front line workers had more positive attitudes towards patient safety after watching this video.

(Indre Brasaitė et.al, 2015) This paper talks about health care provider's attitudes regarding patient safety with the objective of to find out the existing knowledge about health care provider's attitudes related to patient safety. A systematic exploratory review was used in this study with the participants of all health care professionals. Qualitative content analysis was carried out into the study. The results are considered a highly improved attitude towards patient safety in the hospital.

(Hanife Durgan et.al, 2018) This research paper studied about the study of the attitudes of casualty department nurses towards patient safety with the objective of the study is to know about the attitudes of casualty department nurses towards safety measures in hospital. An observational research study was used. The sample of this study are nurses and the data was collected by the usage of tools such as "Information Questionnaire" and "Patient Safety Attitudes Scale". The findings are showed that the average level of the attitudes of casualty nurses towards patient safety.

(A Nabhan et.al, 2007) This paper talks about studied on learning and attitudes towards safety in obstetrics with the objective of this study was to evaluate attitudes of health care workers towards patient safety. A prevalence-observational study design was used in this study. Data was collected in all health care workers. The findings are showed that the most of the respondents are positive (36%).

(Atallah A Hababbeh et.al, 2020) This paper talks about the impact of course outline on the attitudes towards patient safety of emergency department nurses. An experimental study design preliminary and post-intervention was conducted in this study. Data was collected in 66 nurses. The results are showed that there was a inverse correlation between working experience and staff nurses attitude towards safety of the patients.

(Georgeena Elsa Jose et.al, 2017) This research paper studied on to estimate the attitude of hand hygiene in a hospital setup with aimed at investigate the attitude with regard to personal hygiene. A prevalence study was used in the article with the participants of 300 health care workers and a self-structured attitude questionnaire and checklist should be given. The result showed that least attitude with staff nurse better than medical practitioners. Medical practitioners and staff nurses had better practices of hand hygiene.

(Henok Birsaw et.al,2020) This article talks about the knowledge and attitude of care taker towards safety and its associated factors with the aim of estimate the knowledge, attitude and associated factors towards safety among care takers. A cross-sectional analysis was used and provided to 386 care takers using preliminary analysis, self-structured questionnaire and the result show that 52% had low knowledge about patient safety but better attitude towards safety.

(Rintu Jayan et.al, 2019) This research paper studied on attitude of caregiver students towards personal hygiene with the aim of the study to evaluate the attitude regarding hand hygiene among students of health care providers. A descriptive- quantitative research design, purposive sampling technique was used and data collected with 100 samples with health care professionals. The result showed that have most favourable attitude towards hand hygiene.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design and simple probability sampling technique were utilised in this study. A Structured questionnaire with five-point likert scale will be adopted to collect the data. The questionnaire is circulated to 60 health care professionals. The collected data is analysed using frequency, mean, independent sample T-test, and ANOVA.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Research Hypotheses:

- Null Hypothesis (H_0) - The hospital employees show positive attitudes towards safe and hygienic practice.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1) - The hospital employees show negative attitudes towards safe and hygienic practice.

Frequency and Percentage on Demographic Variables.

Figure1: This figure shows the frequency analysis of age of the health care professional health care professionals are under the age of 21-25 years (65.6%) followed by minority of the Employees are under the age of 31-40 years and above 40 years (3.3%).

Figure 2: It shows that the frequency analysis of gender of the health care professionals are under the male gender (53.3%) was highly responded than female gender (45.9%).

Figure 3: It shows that the frequency analysis of the education of the majority of the respondents are B.Sc. Nursing (37.7%) and minimum respondents are in paramedicals (9.8%).

Figure 4: It shows that the frequency analysis of the work shift of the health care professionals under the majority of the respondents are Morning shift (80%) followed by afternoon shift (8.6%), night shift (8.6%) and evening shift (2.9%).

Figure 5: It shows that the frequency analysis of the work place in the hospital of the employees. It is clear from the figure that the majority of the respondents are worked in ward (54.3%) followed by ICU (40%) and emergency department (5.7%).

TABLE 1: To analyse the Attitude towards safe and hygienic practice among Health Care Professionals (HCPs).

S. No.	Attitude Towards Patient Safety	Mean Analysis	Rank
1.	Wearing mask is compulsory in the hospital	3.73	9
2.	Maintaining your hand hygiene	4.03	2
3.	You should follow a proper sanitization techniques	3.93	6
4.	It is mandatory to follow safety measure while giving medication	4.10	1
5.	You should stick on to the duty timing	3.98	4
6.	You should identify the patient based on the tags	4.02	3
7.	You should follow the proper communication to the patients while explaining the procedures	3.85	8
8.	You should give proper information about the drugs before administering to the patients	4.03	2
9.	You have a proper procedure to identify the patient under mental illness	3.95	5
10.	You should follow a proper sterilization techniques while handling patients ICU or OT	3.87	7

This table shows that Mean analysis of Attitude towards safe and hygienic practice of the health care workers (HCPs) is highest weightage in safety measures while giving medications (4.10), and lowest weightage is wearing masks (3.73).

Table 2: To study the significant relationship between the attitudes of employees towards safe and hygienic practice with respect to Gender.

Sn o	Attitude towards safe and hygienic practice	Gender	
		T	Sig
1.	Wearing mask is compulsory in the hospital	1.236	0.222
2.	Maintaining your hand hygiene	1.008	0.318
3.	You should follow a proper sanitization technique.	0.883	0.381
4.	It is mandatory to follow safety measure while giving medication	1.311	0.196
5.	You should stick on to the duty timing	0.463	0.645
6.	You should identify the patient based on the tags	1.165	0.249
7.	You should follow the proper communication to the patients while explaining the procedures	2.707	0.009*
8.	You should give proper information about the drugs before administering to the patients	1.769	0.082
9.	You have a proper procedure to identify the patient under mental illness	2.111	0.039*
10.	You should follow a proper sterilization techniques while handling patients ICU or OT	1.926	0.059

The result shows that there is a no significant relationship between the changes in attitude of employees with respect to the Gender.

Table 3: To study the Significant relationship between the attitudes of employees towards safe and hygienic practice with respect to Work position, Regular shift and Place of work.

S.NO.	Attitude towards safe and hygienic practice	Work position		Regular shift		Place of work	
		F	SIG	F	SIG	F	SIG
1.	Wearing mask is compulsory in the hospital	1.234	.307	2.012	.123	.609	.612
2.	Maintaining your hand hygiene	1.114	.977	.922	.436	.536	.660
3.	You should follow a proper sanitization technique.	.661	.622	2.865	.045*	.080	.971
4.	It is mandatory to follow safety measure while giving medication	.271	.895	1.097	.358	.029	.993
5.	You should stick on to the duty timing	1.461	.226	3.868	.014*	.947	.424
6.	You should identify the patient based on the tags	.738	.570	2.450	.073	.651	.585
7.	You should follow the proper communication to the patients while explaining the procedures	2.232	.077	3.649	.018*	.111	.953
8.	You should give proper information about the drugs before administering to the patients	1.657	.173	2.814	.047*	.172	.915
9.	You have a proper procedure to identify the patient under mental illness	0.618	.652	1.765	.164	.612	.610
10.	You should follow a proper sterilization techniques while handling patients ICU or OT	2.528	.051	2.576	.063	.448	.720

(*-Significant)

The result shows that there is a no significant relationship between change in attitude of employees with respect to the work position, regular shift and place of work.

CONCLUSION

Attitude towards patient safety is more important while handling the patients. If it is followed properly through and innovative best treatments one can eliminate risk of medical errors and nosocomial infection and it will leads to health wellbeing of an all individuals. This study focussed on the demographic variables and its influence on attitude of the employees towards patient's safety. Most of the employees shows positive attitude towards safe and hygienic practise to be followed. This research may be extended in the future with different care services. Rendering a quality care is very vital but, it should be followed by each and every employee in the organization. Quality care can be ensured with evidence-based practise. For which, hospital Accreditation is very important for all the hospitals in the mere future.

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